

4D Geo Modelling from Different Sources at Large Scale

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Abstract

Imagine you're exploring the historic center of a city with its impressive town houses, churches and monuments. What if you could just use your mobile device to find out about the historic buildings around you, making history come alive before your eyes? Within the Jena4D research group we are investigating and developing methods and technologies for automatizing and scaling up the transfer of historical media and their contextual information into a 4D – 3D spatial and temporal scaled – visualization to support research and education on urban history. In this paper we share and discuss a proof of concept for scaling up our data retrieval and modelling pipeline to world scale and first tests for city-based experiences in 7 countries.

CCS Concepts

• Applied computing → Arts and humanities.

Keywords

4D modelling pipeline; mobile visualization; cultural heritage

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1 Introduction

3D or 4D – comprising 3D space and time - models of cultural heritage comprise (a) digitized models of extant objects, captured by different acquisition technologies as e.g. laser scanners, photogrammetry, tomographs etc. [5]. (b) 3D reconstructions of no more extant or never realized cultural heritage. This later type is not directly scannable but can be created only from historical sources as imagery, texts, plans, material remains etc. [11]

2 Current situation

3D/4D reconstructions of no more extant architecture are still almost solely created via manual work. This requires (a) significant amounts of work for source interpretation and model creation [10], (b) is done in highly varying, interdisciplinary workflows which are intransparent and hard to reproduce with (c) processes and results highly purpose-specific. Within our research we are investigating and developing methods and technologies for automatizing and scaling up the transfer of historical media and their contextual information into a 4D – 3D spatial and temporal scaled - model to support research and education on urban history. Content is made accessible as a location-dependent virtual reality 4D browser application for mobile devices and a 4D desktop browser application. Since a previous article stated about the pipeline and state of research and development [12] the aim of this article is to report about the currently ongoing work to scale up the 4D modelling pipeline to world scale. Specific topics include the large scale retrieval and storage of 3D and image data from various sources, the processing via parametric modelling approaches and finally the testing for city experiences in 7 countries.

3 4D geo modelling

Our pipeline comprises three steps: (1) to collect data as images, models and information from multiple sources and via automated and community-based approaches (c.f. Fig. 1), to (2) automatically form a model of a historical architecture and cityscapes via a 4D reconstruction from historical sources. The model is made accessible in two ways of (3) visualization; via a 4D browser and a location-dependent augmented reality (AR) representation.

3.1 Data collection

To gather data on the world scale, we have setup a server-sided pipeline to retrieve data from different providers. Data retrieval comprises approaches to gather images, links to information resources, and 3D models from different sources. To retrieve legally accessible images, we selected CC-0 or CC-BY licensed content only. For data retrieval, we used a series of server-side scripts in Python and PHP feeding into an SQL database and Unix file storage. The scripts process locations called in in our mobile application – the locations are resolved into placenames via Geonames [3]. To avoid reloading already retrieved positions, each object's geocoordinates were processed into geotiles. These geotiles are compiled from the Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) hours and minutes

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Figure 1: General process flow for using the Zenodo API to manage persistent data representations, including pre-processing, upload, update and retrieval operations

of each value. For instance, the geotile 5105×1374 would comprise a bounding box with latitudes 51.05 to 51.06 and longitudes 13.74 to 13.75. Unless this simple approach leads to varying tile sizes, it enables human-readable coding and decoding of geotiles. To query multiple images in services like Google Street View with one result per query we further subdivided the coordinates within the bounding box. By mid 2024 the following data has been retrieved:

- Images: Image retrieval pipeline for contemporary / historic photographs based on requested locations: Europeana, Wikimedia Commons, Flickr, Google Street View, Fortepan, Mapillary, Currently: 220.000 images
- Modelling: World scale elevation model, building footprints + landmarks as 3D buildings: OSM, Objaverse 1.0 and XL, Currently: 400.000 building geometries; 73.000 3D models of cultural heritage; world-scale DEM (50m grid)
- Texts: World-scale information as POIs; annotated texts: Wikipedia, Google Places

Storage at Zenodo. To ensure long-term availability and citability, building models and image sources have been uploaded to Zenodo [13], currently comprising 16,438 images and 63,914 3D models, which are accompanied by Europeana Data Model (EDM) and METS/MODS XMLs (Fig. 1). In processing the visual data, particular attention has been paid to privacy concerns. A two-stage process involving person detection and detailed segmentation has been implemented to mask individuals while preserving as much architectural visual material as possible. Thumbnails of the 3D models were rendered from five perspectives and in various resolutions using an automated pipeline to address different immediate use cases. To manage this amount of data and its versions, a database is updated in real-time with each upload or update process. This database is accompanied by a dashboard and an API, enabling the retrieval of the latest direct links to the model or image sources on Zenodo besides contextual information like data types, previous version DOIs or dataset identifiers. In addition, the latest DOIs are stored in the object data of the 4D applications and will therefore be available through its API. Each Zenodo record contains extracted and aggregated metadata, tables with direct links to main files and thumbnails as well as changelogs. Using the dashboard, directly exporting CSVs of query results allow direct implementations of

Figure 2: 4D modelling pipeline

the data hosted on Zenodo without any additional queries. While retrievals from Zenodo are limited, the current rate is sufficient for positional field-of-view applications in real-time. This approach not only secures the data, but also facilitates its use in scientific, educational and creative contexts.

3.2 4D modelling pipeline

Recent approaches focus on the 3D spatial visualization of contemporary city scenes via view synthesis (recent overview: [9]) or parametric 3D model generation (e.g. [22]) focus on digital images only. Our approach uses both, digital and non digital-born imagery to parametric reconstruct time-varying 4D models of the city. Time information is currently taken from provided metadata. The pipeline (c.f. Fig 2) includes to create building geometries parametrically from building footprints. This step is currently done semi-automatically for historic plans (described in [12]) and use the already vectorized OSM building layer to retrieve and process contemporary buildings at large scale. A following step creates the 3D building by extruding the footprints to building walls, and calculate the roof shape. In another pipeline step the spatialization of photographs takes place. Recent developments in our pipeline included to detecting and eliminating doppelgangers and challenging images. A final step is to map the photographs according to the calculated position and orientation onto the façade and adjust the height of both, facade and roof according to the projected photographs.

Generating large-scale contemporary city models from OSM data. Open Street Map is used for modelling cities up to the level of detail (LoD) 1 - as block models of buildings. The vector building footprints obtained from OSM also provide the height and in some cases the roof shape information as their attributes. We import city

Figure 3: Imported model and images from Overpass and GSV APIs

Figure 4: Sequencing a roof (left); segmenting complex roof structures into smaller segments (middle), HEAT extracted features (right) [4]

models from the overpass turbo API of Open Street Map. These imported 3D buildings from overpass API are of decent quality and have the potential for texturisation. We extrude these models in the browser applications based on the height or storey information in OSM (Fig. 3).

Roof feature generation. For calculating the roof features there are various parametric modelling available. In our work we implemented two approaches: (1) the straight skeleton approach [17] to compute a mediated ridgeline of the roof (e.g., [1, 18]) and (2) a subdividing approach. The latter approach has been developed to deal with roofs having multiple ridgelines as this often occurs for historical buildings. approach is designed to create different roof shapes, which are to be compared and selected for the best match to photographs. For the latter approach algorithm can be divided into two main parts: parts for squared and non-squared roofs. squared roofs are built after calculating the midpoint of the four vertices, and according to the roof shape, the geometry (triangles) is created (Fig. 4). For L-shaped roofs, more properties need to be calculated. First of all, the two shortest distances of the six-vertices roof are calculated.

These lines cannot be neighboring lines (they cannot have the same starting or ending point) and cannot be parallel (their dot product of vectors, created at midpoint, has to be much smaller than one). Then, at the mentioned midpoints, perpendicular lines are created. The crossing point creates a new vertex which combines two parts of the L-shaped roof. At the given height and shifted by some distance, vertices are added at the midpoints of the shortest lines to create the L-shaped top of the roof. Then, triangles are created based on the direction and the newly created vertices.

Another method for identifying the roof shapes would come from a data-driven approach where roof extraction models like HEAT (Holistic Edge Attention Transformer for Structured Reconstruction) [4] and Conv-MPN (Convolutional Message Passing Neural

Figure 5: An SfM reconstruction of the center of Budapest exclusively using historical photographs. Each red pyramid represents one photograph and its orientation and camera parameters

Network for Structured Outdoor Architecture Reconstruction) [6] will be used. These models are trained to extract vectorized roof shapes, including buildings' ridgelines. However, since the accuracy of the results depends on the areas where the model is trained, and may give precisely delineated vectors of building roofs for simpler structures, they still underperform with highly complex structures. Training and validating the model on our custom datasets could improve the accuracy

The next step is to combine results from both parametric roof generators and these models which will help validate and propose a more generalized yet close to real shapes of the roofs. Missing lines from the results of HEAT/Conv-MPN will be completed by a parametric generator (which comes from OSM data) and statistics from HEAT will be used in selecting the best-fitting roof shape produced by the former.

Image spatialization of historic images. Historic datasets are more challenging to work with due to their varied nature and lack of calibration. To improve the quality of the reconstruction, we use several steps to clean the data and set better initialization. When using data from multiple archives, it is possible to have duplicates of the same photographs, either as exact copies, re-scans, or with different post-processing steps (color, resolution, compression). It is also common to have multiple photos from the same or similar camera positions (narrow baseline) with only slight variations, such as moving people or vehicles. Working with duplicate images causes the pipeline to treat 2D-3D feature matches as more certain than they actually are because the track length gets longer. This also disregards the filtering criteria for track length. We use the approach described in [14] to detect duplicates and remove the one with smaller resolution or worse quality (compression artifact, etc.). Certain photographs have extreme aspect ratios, which indicate a stitched panorama photo or an image crop. Both of these categories pose challenges for reconstruction, as they violate the assumptions typically made by reconstruction algorithms. Historic photographs usually lack intrinsic camera parameters. Sometimes, this information is incorrectly filled in with the focal length at digitization

Figure 6: Image to model matching: Height assessment via SIHE (top line), image to 3D matching (bottom line)

instead of the actual camera parameters. Otherwise, the focal length is initialized by a default value as in Colmap [16]. This can cause problems when the actual focal length is vastly different from the initialization, such as with a telephoto lens, because large changes in focal lengths are filtered out. We propose to initialize the focal length of every photo using learned methods such as Dust3r [20] or Mast3r [7]. To test this pipeline on a larger scale, we selected 10 k images as belonging to the same continuous city model of Budapest. Figure 5 depicts an SfM reconstruction using SOTA and -content-based image retrieval (EigenPlaces) and neural matching algorithms (DISK features [19] with LightGlue [8]). Recent improvements included particularly the detection and elimination of doppelgangers and images with challenging conditions. Finally, 1305 images are correctly registered into a single continuous model covering approximately 2.56 km² area and several smaller disconnected ones (individual squares, buildings). Image quality is only checked by the number of inlier (correct) matches during SfM. Neural image quality assessment techniques favour good composition/vibrant colours, which is orthogonal to our selection objectives, with blur and grain do not significantly affect the reconstruction.

Extraction of height attributes. For most model geometries no information about exact height is available. For Google Street view imagery we solve this issue by doing segmentation of the images and calculating the height of the facade and roof image sprites. A height calculation of features is done via SIHE [21] and then used as height information for the parametric building generation (Fig. 6). A step currently in development is to propose and test height information by projecting and testing on the 3D geometries.

Scene compilation. The 4D scene is assembled as a baseline view including a digital elevation model and OSM buildings generated on the user device. Raster images are dynamically projected as textures onto the 3D geometries in the browser viewport, including Google Street View images for contemporary views and the spatialised historic images for historic scenes. Links to external information such as websites are included as 3D POIs. Where available, we replace the low detail OSM models with higher resolution 3D mesh models of either entire cities or specific objects as e.g. sculptures or buildings. For those meshes we calculate bounding boxes and do not show OSM structures within these boxes. From these different data sources scenes are compiled as 4D geotiles (depending on

Figure 7: 4D model - viewport examples

time and location), which are dynamically loaded into the front-end applications at runtime (see Figure 6). A key feature of the pipeline is a CMS like editing mode to enable content creators to create scenes for specific cities. For testing this functionality we are collaborating with several institutions, resulting in curated scenes in currently 7 countries:

- Amsterdam: Valkenbourg at 1800 modelled by UaV
- Dresden: 3D model with various time layers and 5000+ images
- Czech Republic: 3D scan of Castle Pejnstjen
- Valais: 3D city model with 3 time layers reconstructed by EPFL
- Trento: 3D reconstruction of the historical states by FBK
- Budapest: 200k images of historic Budapest
- Leuven: university quarter 3D model created by FU Leuven
- Jena: 5,000 images and 3 time-layers of cadastral data

4 Visualization

Since 2016 our group has developed a modular 4D web-visualization software framework for 4D city and 4D content browsing to test and validate design hypotheses in virtual, augmented, and 2.5D visualization on mobile and desktop devices. As user acceptance of native applications is decreasing [2], especially for specific and short-term use, as relevant for most cityscape scenarios [15] this is a browser-based web application.

4.1 4D application for mobile devices

The 4D City application for mobile devices enables time-variant virtual 3D impressions of historic cities to a multi-device visual interface (Fig. 9) – capable to being accessed via desktop, mobile devices, via AR and VR glasses. The 4D City application does focus on the application layer and do feed in-time from other data providers without a own database except for caching. It enables virtual city tours and past-plays as e.g. mixed-reality escape or discovery games and provide access to knowledge assets from open source platforms such as Wikipedia or tourist information platforms as Triposo. Unique features of that application include a dynamic shader which is capable to create the 4D environments on the fly.

Figure 8: User interface of the mobile application

4.2 4D Browser for desktops

The 4D Browser is used for the information presentation and as a research tool. Linking digital images and their actual location allow for example to directly present resources and therefore proves a valuable support tool for historic research (Fig. 10). Users of the virtual archives can benefit extensively from effective searching functions and tools which work not only content- and theme-based but also location-based. A timeline provides filtering photos of different building conditions.

Figure 9: User interface of the desktop application

5 Outlook

At the current state the applications are already available to provide a contemporary viewer functionality at world scale with location-based Wikipedia articles included as POIs. The 4D retrieval and modelling pipelines are currently at a proof of concept level. Next step will be to complete the pipeline, develop and re-use testable datasets to benchmark the pipeline steps. As an ongoing development step we currently prepare for a better integration of the large number of 3D meshes in the 4D scenes. Related tasks include (1) spatial information retrieval via named entities recognised in captions or image similarity searches between renderings and Wikimedia images. (2) We do currently test the spatial matching between renderings and photographs with known spatial parameters to retrieve the position, orientation and scale of the 3D meshes. Another important task is to enrich the number and coherence of visualisations. This is targeted by a starting project to integrate content already available in Europeana and the European Data Space for Cultural Heritage, but also by enhancing and documenting community functionalities to enable content and scene creation by a wider audience.

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